

Integrated smarthouse application

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In order to utilize the full potential of the smart grid. It is important to enable the consumer to act upon price changes. Since the price, in general, are low compared to the estimate price per hour the consumer makes, this process should be automated, in order for the consumer to gain a economy advantages. Furthermore, it would allow the consumers to change their consumption without having to take active decisions and to do this at a speed where the system can play a role in stabilizing the smart grid, in times of over or under production of electricity.

The system are built from a central IT controller, that receives data from a range of different electrical installations or sensor when available. This information is used to plan the consumption of electricity or other utilities in order to maximize the saving for the consumer. The second part of the system is a central server unit that is used for sending messages or receiving remote commands.

In order to secure, the consumers' confidence it is deemed important to give the consumers access and overview of a system that is transparent in the decisions made. It is important that the consumer is conscious about the system is saving them money but that the system is not wasting the consumer's time with minor decisions.

When the system is monitoring the consumption, relative simple to use the system for other purposes includes other services. This include everything from rising alarms if fires or gas is detected, detect inactivity or death and help people with dementia by reminding them what they were doing or turn of the gas for them.

The system can help with a variety of problems for the modern family and help them improve their living condition, by taking care of small operation. At the same time, it can insure savings for the consumer as well as the society and increase security and comfort. It further more can provide the energy sector with a greater view on what is going on in the grid, and the expected consumption for the coming hour or day.